

Condensation of *p*-Fluorophenylacetic Acid with Aldehydes

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p-Fluorophenylacetic acid was condensed with some substituted benzaldehydes in order to compare its reactivity with the reactivities of *p*-chloro¹, *p*-bromo^{2,3} and *p*-iodophenylacetic⁴ acids. Fluorine substituted compounds have not been tried in Knoevenagel's reaction as yet. As fluorine is a strong electron acceptor, it was thought that it should be more reactive than other halogen substituted phenylacetic acids (in Knoevenagel's reaction) but on account of paucity of the material, the desired number of experiments could not be carried out.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of p-Fluorophenylacetic acid: It was prepared through the following reaction sequence

Condensation of p-fluorophenylacetic acid

With Benzaldehyde: *p*-Fluorophenylacetic acid (0.15 gm) and benzaldehyde (0.10 gm) were taken in a 50 c.c. round bottom flask fitted with reflux condenser and heated at different temperatures viz., 80, 100 and 120° for different durations of time viz., 6, 12 and 18 hrs. in presence of different bases, viz., piperidine and a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride. The resulting mass in each case was extracted with ether and treated with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution. The solution was filtered off. The filtrate on acidification with conc. HCl gave α -carboxy-4-fluorostilbene, m.p. 169° (reported m.p. 167–8°)⁵. Maximum yield of 40.2% of the condensed product was obtained when the reactants were heated at 100° for 12 hrs. in the presence of piperidine.

With Salicylaldehyde: The above procedure was repeated in these condensations also. The condensed mass in each case was treated with 10% sodium bicarbonate solution

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and the solution was warmed. The solution was then filtered off. The residue, which was neutral, was recrystallised from acetone and water (1 : 2) and was found to be 3-(*p*-fluorophenyl)-coumarin m.p. 182° (reported m.p. 185°)⁶.

DISCUSSION

p-Fluorophenylacetic acid has been condensed with benzaldehyde and salicylaldehyde. Maximum yields obtained were 40.2% and 50.0% respectively in the presence of piperidine as catalyst and 0.00% and 75.9% respectively in presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride. The percentage yields in the condensation of *p*-chlorophenylacetic acid with above aldehydes were 55.4% and 30.3% respectively in presence of piperidine as a catalyst and 0.00% and 99.5% respectively in presence of a mixture of pyridine and acetic anhydride. It can therefore, be seen that at least in the condensation with salicylaldehyde in presence of piperidine as a catalyst, it is more reactive than other halogens substituted aldehydes. As, it was rather difficult to prepare appreciable quantities of *p*-Fluorophenylacetic acid, on account of the very low yields obtained in its preparation, it was not possible to carry out more experiments with different aldehydes. It is, therefore, difficult to compare the reactivity of *p*-fluorophenylacetic acid with the reactivities of *p*-chloro-, *p*-bromo- and *p*-iodophenylacetic acids, on the basis of the above results alone. The above results, however, indicate that it is possible to condense *p*-fluorophenylacetic acid with some aldehydes.

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